

DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF SATIRICAL MEMES AS GRAPHIC INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS IN TEACHING PHILIPPINE POLITICS AND GOVERNANCE

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to develop and evaluate satirical memes as graphic instructional materials in teaching Philippine Politics and Governance for Senior High School Learners. The study used Design and Development Research (DDR) to build an empirical basis for developing instructional content on the graphic instructional material. In addition, the researcher used a quantitative descriptive research design, to assess the generated satirical memes as graphic instructional materials in terms of the intellectual property rights compliance, content and instructional quality indicators provided in the adopted and modified Learning Resources Management and Development System (LRMDS) evaluation tool. The study was conducted during the school year 2022-2023 in different public secondary schools in the City Schools Division of Antipolo City. The developed satirical memes as graphic instructional materials were evaluated by a panel of ninety-six professionals consist of eighty-four public secondary school teachers of Social Studies and twelve teachers in the Department of Social Sciences make up the expert group. The experts and teachers were selected using the simple random sampling method. The findings of the study revealed that the developed satirical memes as graphic instructional materials as evaluated by the experts and teachers of Social Studies which signifies a high level of validity. This implies that the developed satirical memes as graphic instructional materials are appropriate, and focused on the goals, and that expert and teacher evaluation of the materials do not differ significantly when it comes to their suitability for teaching Philippine Politics and Governance.

Keywords: *Satirical Memes, development, evaluation, content, intellectual property rights compliance, instructional quality*

INTRODUCTION

Teachers are expected to incorporate as many technology items as possible to facilitate the participation of students in classroom activities (Purnama, 2017). According to Republic Act 10533, Section 10.3 mandates the creation of teaching and learning resources (Enhanced Basic Education Act, 2013). Additionally, DepEd Order No. 35, s. 2016 invites educators to enhance the educational process by incorporating information and communication technology (ICT) solutions that are suitable for students' development (DepEd, 2016).

With the sudden emergence of the internet, post-millennials have created a modern satirical medium of art known as memes. Internet memes, which became popular in 2006, come in different shapes and sizes. The term "meme" originated from evolutionary biology, specifically coined by Richard Dawkins in his renowned 1976 book, "The Selfish Gene." A meme represents a unit of cultural transmission or imitation (Aslan, 2018). The study published by Diaz (2013) stated that memes can be created or based on a real-life occurrence that goes viral on the internet, allowing others to replicate it. It usually spreads in the same way, but it can also spread through transitions. Also, Internet memes are groups of digital items or texts that many people create and share separately but are aware of each other and have the same features, content, shape, and place (Shifman, 2014).

Evidently, internet memes are deeply ingrained in daily lives, and they may be quickly accessed or created with just a few touches on a mobile phone screen. They are part of the digital community in which students are engaged inevitably (Sorte, 2019). As a result, using memes as a teaching tool aims to bridge the gap between student characteristics, rapid technology improvements, and the constant need to renew efforts to enhance their achievements is recommended (Purnama et al, 2018).

Memes are currently being used widely and popularly in educational settings as well. Memes are intertextual, which makes them an excellent tool for learning by allowing students to make connections across and between courses (Garg, 2021). Also, memes, as a new sort of medium, can visually convey the content of students' learning and can be altered and utilized. Since their inception, students have recognized and acknowledged them as objects. Memes can efficiently transfer educational content and serve as a bridge and link between teachers and students as a carrier of ideological and political education (Dongqiang et al, 2020). Therefore, memes play an important function in education, as demonstrated by the studies conducted by Garg (2021). Memes can also be effective teaching aids that cross disciplinary boundaries and promote interaction between teachers and students. Teachers may successfully communicate complicated concepts in a visually interesting way by utilizing memes, which will ultimately improve student learning and foster deeper understanding.

Moreover, Wells conducted study in 2018 explained that making memes about current events helped people improve their critical thinking skills as well as their understanding of current events. Therefore, to grasp a meme, the reader must be familiar with all these aspects of culture, which makes meme learning a multidisciplinary process (Baran, 2013). In addition, the utilization of memes in the classroom is not only funny but also educational (Harshavardhan & Kumar, 2019). Moreover, the study by Baysac (2017) supports the idea that using memes allows students to focus and maintain their interest in the material while also honing their analytical and critical thinking skills, since memes have the ability to both amuse and stimulate thought.

Similarly, Gagaza (2020) concluded that Internet Memes-Enhanced Instruction (IMI) is a useful method for helping students improve their correlational thinking abilities. By employing memes as instructional materials, students can interact with course content in a unique and memorable way, ultimately enhancing their overall learning experience and cognitive abilities.

Amidst the growing number of literatures that see satirical memes as a possible teaching tool to develop learners holistically, both locally and globally, it is the objective of the researcher to present new knowledge in the development of a material that introduces satirical memes in social science subjects. Recognizing the importance of enhancing teaching materials that resonate with learners' interests and learning abilities and considering the limited studies utilizing memes in social science subjects, there is a clear need to develop satirical memes as engaging instructional materials for social science subjects. This effort aims to increase students' knowledge and engagement in political topics, utilizing memes to foster critical thinking skills among Senior High School students. Therefore, this study focuses on developing and evaluating satirical memes as graphic instructional materials for teaching Philippine Politics and Governance.

Research Questions

The main problem of the study is to develop and evaluate satirical memes as graphic instructional materials in teaching Philippine Politics and Governance. Specifically, it aims to answer the following questions:

1. How does the satirical memes as graphic instructional materials in teaching Philippine Politics and Governance for senior high school learners developed?
2. How do the experts and teachers evaluate the satirical memes as graphic instructional materials in teaching Philippine Politics and Governance for senior high school learners developed with respect to:
 - 2.1 intellectual property rights compliance;
 - 2.2 content;
 - 2.3 instructional quality?
3. Is there a significant difference on the evaluation of experts and teachers on the developed satirical memes as graphic instructional materials in teaching Philippine Politics and Governance for senior high school learners with respect to the above-mentioned variables?

4. What output can be proposed based on the results of the study?

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a **Design and Development Research (DDR)** approach to create and empirically ground satirical memes as graphic instructional materials for teaching Philippine Politics and Governance. The development process was based on the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) prescribed for the subject. To evaluate the materials, a **descriptive evaluative research design** was employed.

The study was conducted during the 2022-2023 school year within public secondary schools of Antipolo City. Participants included 12 Social Sciences experts and 84 Social Studies teachers, randomly selected through **simple random sampling** from a population of 106 respondents using Slovin's Formula with a 5% margin of error. The experts were distinguished educators with significant teaching experience and advanced degrees, while the teachers were public secondary school instructors.

Evaluation of the satirical memes was performed using a modified version of the Department of Education's Learning Resources Management and Development System (LRMDS) evaluation tool, focusing on intellectual property rights compliance, content quality, and instructional effectiveness. Data were collected through a structured questionnaire designed from the adapted LRMDS tool.

For data analysis, **mean scores** were calculated to determine the evaluation ratings from experts, while an **independent t-test** was used to assess any significant differences between expert and teacher evaluations. The study adhered to the Data Privacy Act, ensuring confidentiality and anonymity of respondents.

This research was limited to the development and evaluation phases and did not include the actual classroom implementation of the satirical memes. The results provide foundational insights into the suitability of these graphic instructional materials for teaching Philippine Politics and Governance in senior high school.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Design and Development of Satirical Memes as Graphic Instructional Materials in teaching Philippine Politics and Governance for Senior High School Learners

The researcher was inspired and modified the model of the instructional material development used by Gumonan and Bug-os (2021). It follows the procedures used by the said researchers which involves analysis phase, design and development phase, and evaluation phase.

First, the researcher conducted an analysis phase, which involved identifying the essential topics and learning competencies in Philippine Politics and Governance that covered a two-quarter period. In addition, existing Philippine Politics and Governance books and related materials were assessed to identify any gaps in the available resources. The researcher also conducted a review of related literature and studies to determine the benefits of using satirical memes as graphic instructional materials as a teaching tool in different subjects.

Next, the researcher moved to the design and development phase. Learning objectives and content were selected for the satirical memes as graphic instructional materials, and topics from the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) were identified for the entire semester of the course. The developed satirical memes feature unique visual style, incorporating images, graphics, and illustrations that directly relate to political topics. Text is overlaid onto the images, providing context, commentary, or humor that reinforces the message. The content of these satirical memes includes humor, sarcasm, or irony to critique societal issues or convey political opinions. Cultural references and symbols were also incorporated to resonate with the audience and enhance relevance. In terms of usage, satirical memes serve as effective tools for engaging learners and simplifying complex topics. It stimulates interest and facilitate understanding by presenting political concepts in a relatable and accessible format. The researcher sought expert opinions to ensure that the materials complied with intellectual property laws, had high-quality content, and were effective teaching tools for the intended audience.

The evaluation of the developed satirical memes as graphic instructional materials involved a comprehensive process of refinement and adaptation. Drawing from the Learning Resources Management and Development System, the researcher implemented a modified evaluation tool to assess the effectiveness of these materials. A panel of 96 professionals, comprising both public secondary school teachers and social science experts from the Department of Social Sciences, undertook the meticulous task of evaluating the satirical memes against criteria such as intellectual property compliance, content, and instructional quality.

Following the assessment, the expert panel provided invaluable feedback, ideas, and recommendations that guided the subsequent redesign of the satirical memes. This iterative process ensured that the instructional materials were optimized to meet the specific needs of senior high school learners and effectively communicate concepts related to Philippine Politics and Governance. The incorporation of expert insights underscored the commitment to continuous improvement and alignment with educational objectives.

The development of satirical memes as graphic instructional materials for teaching Philippine Politics and Governance represents a rigorous process that integrates careful planning, analysis, design, and evaluation. Teachers can improve student engagement and comprehension by using satirical memes, which use humor and visuals to make difficult political ideas more approachable and relatable for students. It highlights how

crucial it is to modify teaching materials to fit the interests and learning preferences of the intended audience, hence increasing the efficacy of learning initiatives in senior high school settings.

Evaluation of the Experts and Teachers on the Developed Satirical Memes as Graphic Instructional Materials in teaching Philippine Politics and Governance with Respect to Intellectual Property Rights Compliance, Content, and Instructional Quality.

Table 1 presents the obtained mean and verbal interpretation on the experts and teacher’s evaluation of the developed satirical memes as graphic instructional materials in teaching Philippine Politics and Governance concerning intellectual property rights compliance.

Table 1
Evaluation of the Experts and Teachers on the Satirical Memes as Graphic Instructional Materials in Teaching Philippine Politics and Governance for Senior High School Learners with respect to Intellectual Property Rights Compliance

A. Intellectual Property Rights Compliance	Expert		Teacher		Overall	
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI
1. The developed Satirical Memes as Graphic Instructional Materials have no copyright violations.	4.08	SA	4.19	A	4.18	A
2. The copyrighted texts and visuals used in the developed Satirical Memes as Graphic Instructional Materials are cited.	4.50	SA	4.38	SA	4.40	SA
3. The copyrighted materials used in the developed Satirical Memes as Graphic Instructional Materials are accurately cited.	4.50	SA	4.39	SA	4.41	SA
Overall	4.36	SA	4.32	SA	4.33	SA

Legend: SA- Strongly Agree A- Agree VI – Value Interpretation

The table shows the evaluation of the experts and teachers on the satirical memes as graphic instructional materials in teaching Philippine Politics and Governance for Senior High School Learners with respect to Intellectual Property Rights Compliance. On the experts side the overall mean is 4.36 which indicates that the experts strongly agreed that the developed satirical memes as graphic instructional materials had complied in the intellectual property rights. On the other hand, the overall mean of the teachers is 4.32 which also indicates that the teachers strongly agreed that the developed satirical memes as graphic instructional materials had complied in the intellectual property rights. Overall, both experts and teachers strongly agreed that the developed satirical memes as graphic

instructional materials had complied in the intellectual property rights as indicated by the overall mean of 4.33.

These findings imply that the two groups of respondents indicate that the developed satirical memes as graphic instructional materials have complied in terms of intellectual property rights. It means that the satirical memes have no copyright violations, and the texts and visuals used in satirical memes as well as the copyrighted materials are accurately cited.

This result is supported from the study of Marciszewski (2020) which proves that many online memes use previously published copyrighted content, even though some of them build upon original or public domain works. The meme author needs to use an affirmative defense to prevent copyright infringement. Observe copyright laws and regulations or assume that using copyrighted content is acceptable use.

For instance, DepEd Order No. 12, s. 2020 acknowledges the importance of adhering to multiple principles of Intellectual Property in relation to the development, manufacture, dissemination, and application of instructional materials. Additionally, according to DepEd Order No. 18, s. 2020, sharing digital files without authorization for purposes other than those intended is prohibited and may result in disciplinary action (Chan et al, 2022).

However, in the study conducted by Kevins (2021) revealed that when a meme maker uses their ingenuity to add a caption or alter the original color effect of a photo, it can be recognized that they have put in enough work to warrant independent copyright protection for themselves.

Academic communities emphasize the importance of complying with copyright laws, as educators are responsible for safeguarding the works of all individuals within the institution and promoting a culture that fosters and protects their creations (de Dios et al, 2022). In the end, we engage in citing to ensure fairness and recognize the accomplishments of those who have preceded us (Hoffmann et al, 2016).

The table shows the evaluation of the experts and teachers on the satirical memes as graphic instructional materials in teaching Philippine Politics and Governance for Senior High School Learners with respect to Content. On the experts side the overall mean is 4.56 which indicates that the experts strongly agreed that the developed satirical memes as graphic instructional materials had an appropriate content. On the other hand, the overall mean of the teachers is 4.46 which also indicates that the teachers strongly agreed that the developed satirical memes as graphic instructional materials had an appropriate content. Overall, both experts and teachers strongly agreed that the developed satirical memes as graphic instructional materials had an appropriate content as indicated by the overall mean of 4.48.

Table 2
Evaluation of the Experts and Teachers on the Satirical Memes as Graphic Instructional Materials in Teaching Philippine Politics and Governance for Senior High School Learners with respect to Content

B. Content	Expert		Teacher		Overall	
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI
1. The developed Satirical Memes as Graphic Instructional Materials reinforce, enrich, and / or lead to the mastery of certain learning competencies and objectives for the level and subject it was intended.	4.58	SA	4.39	SA	4.42	SA
2. The developed Satirical Memes as Graphic Instructional Materials have the potential to arouse interest of the target learners.	4.67	SA	4.50	SA	4.52	SA
3. The facts are relevant in the developed Satirical Memes as Graphic Instructional Materials.	4.50	SA	4.40	SA	4.42	SA
4. Information provided in the developed Satirical Memes as Graphic Instructional Materials are updated.	4.25	SA	4.45	SA	4.43	SA
5. Text and Images are relevant to the topic based on the developed Satirical Memes as Graphic Instructional Materials.	4.42	SA	4.46	SA	4.46	SA
6. Text and Images of the Satirical Memes as Graphic Instructional Materials are clear and adequately convey the message of the subject or topic.	4.67	SA	4.44	SA	4.47	SA
7. The content of the developed Satirical Memes as Graphic Instructional Materials stimulates and promotes critical thinking.	4.75	SA	4.50	SA	4.53	SA
8. The content of the developed Satirical Memes as Graphic Instructional Materials effectively stimulates creativity of the learners.	4.75	SA	4.50	SA	4.53	SA
9. The content of the developed Satirical Memes as Graphic Instructional Materials is logically developed and organized.	4.50	SA	4.49	SA	4.49	SA
10. The content of the developed Satirical Memes as Graphic Instructional Material is relevant to real-life situations.	4.50	SA	4.50	SA	4.50	SA
Overall	4.56	SA	4.46	SA	4.48	SA

These findings imply that the two groups of respondents indicated that the content of the developed satirical memes as graphic instructional materials strongly agreed. This means that when it comes to the content, the developed Satirical Memes as Graphic Instructional Materials reinforce, enrich, and/or lead to the mastery of certain learning competencies and objectives for the level and subject it was intended. It has the potential to arouse the interest of the target learners, the facts are relevant, provided information is updated, text and images of the developed graphic instructional materials are relevant to the topic and adequately convey the message of the subject or topic. Its content stimulates and promotes the critical thinking and creativity of the learners. Also, the

content of the developed Satirical Memes as Graphic Instructional Materials is logically developed and organized, and it is relevant to real-life situations.

This result is supported from the study of Altukruni (2022) which aims to increase students' motivation to learn during the pandemic by using funny memes and technology. It was revealed that the student's cognitive and communicative abilities were found to be improved when memes were used in a virtual learning environment. Additionally, students' knowledge of the connection between language and culture was raised, and their pragmatic competence and inferential skills were enhanced.

Another study that relevant to the content of a graphic instructional material is the study of Wells et al (2020) found out that the internet memes not only engage students and gives them a platform for self-expression, but it also has various educational benefits. It enables learners to see how challenging it is to convey all relevant information in a single meme. It tests learners' ability to construct an argument based on a single meme statement. Finally, it aids in the development of critical thinking abilities in a manner comparable to the conventional argumentative essay.

Table 3
Evaluation of the Experts and Teachers on the Satirical Memes as Graphic Instructional Materials in Teaching Philippine Politics and Governance for Senior High School Learners with respect to Instructional Quality

C. Instructional Quality	Expert		Teacher		Overall	
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI
1. The purpose of the developed Satirical Memes as Graphic Instructional Materials is well defined.	4.42	SA	4.50	SA	4.49	SA
2. The level of difficulty of the developed Satirical Memes as Graphic Instructional Materials are appropriate for the intended target learners.	4.42	SA	4.40	SA	4.41	SA
3. The design and colors of the developed Satirical Memes as Graphic Instructional Materials are used for appropriate instructional reasons.	4.58	SA	4.42	SA	4.44	SA
4. Text and Images of the developed Satirical Memes as Graphic Instructional Materials are suitable to the age level and interests of the target learners.	4.58	SA	4.45	SA	4.47	SA
5. The developed Satirical Memes as Graphic Instructional Materials are enjoyable, stimulating, and engaging.	4.33	SA	4.48	SA	4.46	SA
6. Typographic design of the Satirical Memes as Graphic Instructional Materials facilitates understanding of concepts presented.	4.50	SA	4.33	SA	4.35	SA
7. The developed Satirical Memes as Graphic Instructional Materials are free from any social content violations.	4.17	A	4.39	SA	4.36	SA
8. The developed Satirical Memes as Graphic Instructional Materials are free from factual errors.	4.00	A	4.32	SA	4.28	SA
9. The developed Satirical Memes as Graphic Instructional Materials are free from grammatical errors	4.00	A	4.30	SA	4.26	SA

10. The developed Satirical Memes as Graphic Instructional Materials are free from conceptual errors	4.00	A	4.29	SA	4.25	SA
Overall	4.30	SA	4.39	SA	4.38	SA

The table shows the evaluation of the experts and teachers on the satirical memes as graphic instructional materials in teaching Philippine Politics and Governance for Senior High School Learners with respect to Instructional Quality. On the experts side the overall mean is 4.30 which indicates that the experts strongly agreed that the developed satirical memes as graphic instructional materials had a suitable instructional quality. On the other hand, the overall mean of the teachers is 4.39 which also indicates that the teachers strongly agreed that the developed satirical memes as graphic instructional materials had a suitable instructional quality. Overall, both experts and teachers strongly agreed that the developed satirical memes as graphic instructional materials had a suitable instructional quality as indicated by the overall mean of 4.38.

These findings imply that the two groups of respondents indicate that the instructional quality in the prepared satirical memes as graphic instructional materials are strongly agreed. This means that when it comes to instructional quality, the developed satirical memes have well-defined purpose, its level of difficulty is appropriate for the intended target learners and the design and colors used in the satirical memes are appropriate for instructional reasons. Also, the text and images used in the satirical memes as graphic instructional materials are suitable to the age level and interests of the target learners. They are enjoyable, stimulating, and engaging and the typographic design of the Satirical Memes as Graphic Instructional Materials facilitates understanding of the concepts presented. Free from social content violations, factual errors, grammatical errors, and conceptual errors.

This result is parallel to the study of Marymee (2021) that memes can introduce a novel method of instruction at all educational levels since they may engage students of various learning types. Compared to textual instructions, memes hold students' attention longer and may encourage them to consider their answers more carefully while simultaneously raising interest in the course material.

Another parallel study on the result is the study of Zakharova (2021) which examines the effectiveness of internet memes in increasing learners' motivation to study foreign languages that memes have been discovered to be an effective and useful tool in language classrooms. In both group and individual tasks, they increased the participants' involvement and productivity. They were successful in boosting students' desire to learn.

Table 4
Composite Table on the Evaluation of the Experts and Teachers on the Satirical Memes as Graphic Instructional Materials in Teaching Philippine Politics and Governance for Senior High School Learners

Variables	Expert		Teacher		Grand Mean	
	Overall Mean	VI	Overall Mean	VI	Overall Mean	VI
A. Intellectual Property Rights Compliance	4.36	SA	4.32	SA	4.33	SA
B. Content	4.56	SA	4.46	SA	4.48	SA
C. Instructional Quality	4.30	SA	4.39	SA	4.38	SA
Grand Mean	4.41	SA	4.39	SA	4.39	SA

Table 4 presents the composite table on the experts and teacher's evaluation of the developed satirical memes as graphic instructional materials in teaching Philippine Politics and Governance concerning Intellectual Property Rights Compliance, Content, and Instructional Quality.

It can be seen in the table that the Social Science Experts and Social Studies Teachers strongly agreed on the criteria set in evaluating the satirical memes as graphic instructional materials on the topics of Philippine Politics and Governance as shown by the means of 4.41 and 4.39, respectively average of 4.39.

This implies that the two groups of respondents indicate that all its aspects and indicators such as the intellectual property rights compliance, content, and instructional quality in the prepared satirical memes as graphic instructional materials are highly acceptable and it could be used by the teachers in Philippine politics and governance.

This result is similar to the study of Youssef (2023) where teachers are open to use memes in the classroom. Memes have helped educators build rapport with learners and reduce the affective filter in the classroom. Another study conducted by Batran (2023) Teachers claimed that memes are useful and may be employed in a variety of contexts because they provide a tool or supplement that supports the teacher's goals and improves culture teaching. On the other hand, the study of Anton-Sancho et.al (2022) has been discovered that college professors value the usage of humor resources in virtual learning environments in higher education.

Significant Difference Between the Evaluations of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Developed Satirical Memes as Graphic Instructional Materials in Teaching Philippine Politics and Governance

Table 5 presents the obtained F-value, p-value, and decision of the two groups of respondents on the developed satirical memes as graphic instructional materials in teaching Philippine politics and governance with respect to the above-mentioned variables.

Table 5
Significant Difference on the Evaluation of Experts and Teachers on the Developed Satirical Memes as Graphic Instructional Materials in Teaching Philippine Politics and Governance for Senior High School Learners

Variables	Respondent	Mean	Sd.	df	t-value	p- value	Ho	VI
A. Intellectual Property Rights Compliance	Experts	4.36	.658	94	.188	.851	FR	NS
	Teachers	4.32	.685					
B. Content	Experts	4.56	.547	94	.484	.630	FR	NS
	Teachers	4.46	.640					
C. Instructional Quality	Experts	4.30	.743	94	.395	.694	FR	NS
	Teachers	4.39	.720					
Grand Mean	Experts	4.41	.600	94	.078	.938	FR	NS
	Teachers	4.39	.640					

Legend: df – degrees of freedom H_o - Null hypothesis FR – Failed to Reject NS – Not Significant

The table presents the summary of the test of significant difference between the evaluations of the two groups of respondents on the developed satirical memes as graphic instructional materials in teaching Philippine Politics and Governance in terms of intellectual property rights compliance, content, and instructional quality.

As shown in the table, there is no sufficient evidence at the 0.05 level of significance to show that there is a significant difference in the evaluation of experts and teachers on the developed satirical memes as graphic instructional materials in teaching Philippine Politics and Governance for Senior High School Learners in terms of Intellectual Property Compliance.

In the same table above, the data shows that there is no sufficient evidence at the 0.05 level of significance to show that there is a significant difference in the evaluation of experts and teachers on the developed satirical memes as graphic instructional materials in Teaching Philippine Politics and Governance for Senior High School Learners in terms of Content.

Lastly, the data shows that there is no sufficient evidence at the 0.05 level of significance to show that there is a significant difference on the evaluation of experts

and teachers on the developed satirical memes as graphic instructional materials in Teaching Philippine Politics and Governance for Senior High School Learners in terms of Instructional Quality.

The overall data based on the experts and teachers' findings suggests that at 0.05 level of significance, the obtained data failed to reject the null hypothesis.

This implies that the assessment of the developed satirical memes as graphic instructional materials is suitable, keyed in the objectives, and there is no significant difference on the evaluation of the experts and teachers to the developed satirical memes as graphic instructional materials in teaching Philippine politics and governance.

The findings of the research are parallel to the findings of the study of Yapıcı (2016) which determined that the visual materials, resonate strongly with the role of memes as visual tools in enhancing learning experiences are appropriate for the kids' age level and have the potential to be helpful. Visuals do not only provide a better explanation of the subject but also have the power to draw students' attention to the material, interest, summarize the issue, and have the capacity to support the information provided in the texts the text, pictures have the ability to communicate parallels and contrasts that are difficult for learners to understand in text, by comparing the similarities and contrasts between the past and present using sample images. Memes, on the other hand, are visual messages that have the innate capacity to communicate complicated ideas succinctly and interestingly. Memes are a useful tool for contextualizing and summarizing content, supporting written instruction and enhancing student comprehension.

Summary of Findings

Based on the analyses and interpretation of data gathered, the findings were hereby summarized:

1. Development of Satirical Memes as Graphic Instructional Materials in Teaching Philippine Politics and Governance

The development of satirical memes as graphic instructional materials is systematic because it followed a model of instructional material development inspired by Gumonan & Bug-os (2021) with some modifications applied. It was done through analysis, design and development, and evaluation phase.

2. Evaluation of the Respondents on the Developed Satirical Memes as Graphic Instructional Materials in Teaching Philippine Politics and Governance with respect to Intellectual Property Rights Compliance, Content, and Instructional Quality.

- 2.1 With respect to intellectual property rights compliance, most of the respondents strongly agreed that in terms of Intellectual Property Rights Compliance the texts and visuals used in satirical memes as well as the copyrighted materials are accurately cited.

- 2.2 With respect to content, most of the respondents strongly agreed that the developed satirical memes as graphic instructional materials for Senior High School learners are logically developed and organized, and it is relevant to real-life situations.
- 2.3 With respect to instructional quality, most of the respondents strongly agreed that the satirical memes as graphic instructional materials are enjoyable, stimulating, and engaging to the students and is free from social content violations, factual errors, grammatical errors, and conceptual errors.

3. Significant Difference on the Evaluation of the Two Groups on the Developed Satirical Memes as Graphic Instructional Materials in Teaching Philippine Politics and Governance with Respect to the Above-Mentioned Criteria.

There is no significant difference on the evaluation of the experts and teachers to the developed satirical memes as graphic instructional materials in teaching Philippine politics and governance.

Conclusions

Based on the results of the study, the conclusions below were drawn:

1. The development of satirical memes as graphic instructional materials is possible through the model on instructional material development used by Gumonan & Bug-os (2021) with modifications applied.
2. The instructional quality, intellectual property compliance, and content of using the satirical memes as graphic instructional materials in teaching Philippine Politics and Governance are determined to be relevant in the learning process.
3. The developed satirical memes as graphic instructional materials can be utilized in the class.

Recommendations

In the analysis of the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are hereby presented.

1. Further enhancement and modification by the future researchers may be applied to the satirical memes as graphic instructional materials by the teachers of Philippine politics and governance.
2. Teachers may also use the developed satirical memes as graphic instructional materials to the senior high school students to validate its effectiveness.
3. Teachers handling Philippine Politics and Governance subject may use the developed satirical memes as graphic instructional materials.
4. Future researchers may conduct the same study but may include other social science topics in developing satirical memes as graphic instructional materials.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher hereby declares that the conduct of this study strictly adhered to ethical research standards. Informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to their involvement, and they were made fully aware of their right to withdraw from the study at any point without any form of consequence. The anonymity and confidentiality of all respondents were maintained throughout the research process. The well-being of all participants was given utmost priority, and no form of physical, psychological, or emotional harm was inflicted during the study. The researcher affirms that there is no conflict of interest in the implementation and presentation of this study. Furthermore, academic integrity was strictly observed by avoiding any form of plagiarism and ensuring that all sources were properly acknowledged. The interpretation of findings was conducted objectively, free from any personal or political bias. Lastly, the results of this study were used solely for academic and research purposes, with the intention of contributing to the advancement of instructional strategies in teaching Philippine Politics and Governance.

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